

THE ROLE OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IN THE FORMATION OF YOUTH MIND

Murodov Mashrab Yoqub O'g'li

Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek Lecturer at the Department of "Social Work"
of the National University

E-mail: murodovmashrab06@gmail.com

Phone: 91-961-91-89

Annotation In the current era of globalization, gender issues are one of the important directions of society's life not only in social, but also in spiritual, cultural, and psychological aspects. Gender stereotypes act as an important psychological factor in a person's awareness of their place, role, and opportunities in society. Especially among young people, the ideas formed regarding the roles of men and women directly affect their choice of profession, social activity, and personal life. The study of gender stereotypes is a pressing issue, and these stereotypes serve as an important psychological factor in young people's self-esteem, social relations, and even finding their place in society.

Keywords: Gender stereotype, ability, emotion, social role, career choice, personal value, advertising, family upbringing, critical analysis, gender culture, stereotype.

Concept and essence of gender stereotypes: The concept of a "gender stereotype" refers to a system of stable, often subjective views formed in society regarding the behavior, abilities, emotions, and social roles of men and women. For example, statements such as "a man should be strong, firm, and capable of leadership" and "a woman should be gentle, obedient, and responsible for household chores" are the most common forms of gender stereotypes. Gender stereotypes are a complex of perceptions formed over many years regarding the roles of men and women in society. The following factors influence their formation: Historical factors: since ancient times, men have been engaged in physical labor, warfare, and administration, while women have been engaged in household chores and child-rearing. These roles have become entrenched as social norms over time. Cultural and religious factors - the values, rituals, and religious beliefs of many peoples - have defined the "traditional" roles of men and women. The images of the "ideal man" and "ideal woman" are created through mass media—advertising, films, and social networks. Family and upbringing - starting from childhood, parents assign tasks to children depending on their gender ("You're a girl, be gentle," "You're

a boy, don't cry," etc.). Such perceptions are often associated with culture, religion, traditions, and historical experience, which are firmly rooted in the social consciousness. However, in today's modern society, these stereotypes narrow the worldview of young people and become an obstacle to personal development.

The psychological impact of gender stereotypes on the consciousness of youth. During youth, the process of self-awareness, career choice, and the formation of personal values occurs actively. During this period, gender stereotypes exhibit the following psychological effects: Influence on self-esteem: girls may feel "unfit to lead," while boys may feel the need to "hide their feelings." Impact on career choice: girls tend to choose more "feminine" professions (teacher, nurse, designer), while boys tend to choose "masculine" fields (engineering, IT, business). Impact on interpersonal relationships: due to stereotypes, adolescents may feel uncomfortable in mutual communication or be unable to express their thoughts freely [3]. Young people are highly sensitive to external influences during the process of forming their personality. Gender stereotypes affect their mental world as follows: Decreased self-esteem – girls or boys feel "wrong" or "unfit" when they do not fit the role society expects them to play. Fear and internal barriers - Due to the stereotype that "girls cannot be leaders," many girls give up their leadership positions. Restriction in career choice - if a boy wants to become a teacher, society may evaluate him as having "chosen a women's profession"; this stops young people from realizing their dreams and talents. Problems with self-expression - young people hide their true personal desires while trying to adapt to societal norms [4].

Psychological studies (Eagly, 2019; Bem, 1981) indicates that gender stereotypes limit the process of an individual's self-awareness, inhibit creative thinking, and hinder social adaptation [2].

Analyses indicate that gender stereotypes significantly influence the psychological development of young people. In particular, stereotypes can lower the level of self-esteem among young people, increase internal insecurity, and prevent them from fully realizing their personal potential. Gender stereotypes are particularly pronounced in the process of choosing a profession. Girls are more likely to be oriented toward "traditional" professions, while boys are oriented toward "technical" or "managerial" fields. This leads to the emergence of professional segregation in the labor market. Stereotypes also cause problems in interpersonal relationships. Young people cannot freely express their thoughts and feelings, trying to adapt to the roles assigned by society. This leads to psychological pressure and internal conflicts. The role of the education system, the media, and the family is important in reducing gender

stereotypes. In particular, social stereotypes can be gradually eliminated by instilling ideas of gender equality into the minds of young people [5].

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS Gender stereotypes have a strong impact on the socio-psychological development of young people. They can limit an individual's capabilities, negatively affect self-esteem, career choice, and life direction. Therefore, forming a gender culture in education and family upbringing, critically analyzing stereotypes, and teaching young people to think freely is an important task of modern society.

Developing gender education in curricula - including topics on gender equality, social justice, and human rights in lessons.

Conducting training for parents - fostering a culture of upbringing in children that is not based on gender differences.

Promoting positive gender models in the media - preparing documentaries and interviews about women and men in various professions.

Establishing gender equality as a priority area in state policy.

Organization of social campaigns, competitions, and projects against gender stereotypes among youth.

Establishing psychological consultation centers in educational institutions to encourage young people to freely develop their abilities.

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